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TEACHING RESOURCES

PART 2 - IDENTIFY

HOW TO INCORPORATE
INTERCULTURAL LEARNING INTO
PHYSICAL EDUCATION

CULTURE AND SOCIETY
BUILDING INTERCULTURAL
AND SOCIAL COMPETENCIES
THROUGH PHYSICAL
EDUCATION

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PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL LEARNING

How is PE seen in terms of contribution to society?

The Declaration of Berlin 2013 UNESCO's World Sports Ministers Conference (MINEPS V)

“Physical education (PE) is the most effective means of providing all children and youth with the skills, attitudes, values, knowledge and understanding or lifelong participation in society.”

UNESCO Quality Physical Education

“Quality physical education is a platform for inclusion in wider society, particularly in terms of challenging stigma and overcoming stereotypes (QPE, 2015, pp: 6)

UNESCO International Charter of PE, Physical Activity and Sport

Every human being has a fundamental right to PE, physical activity (PA) and sport without discrimination on the basis of ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property or any other basis.

Cultural diversity in PE, PA and sport forms part of humanity's intangible heritage. The diversity is a basic feature of their value and appeal. Traditional and indigenous games, dances and sports, also in their modern and emerging forms, express the world's rich cultural heritage and must be protected and promoted

Highlighting that the provision of QPE, PA and sport is essential, to realize their full potential to promote values such as fair play, equality, honesty, excellence, commitment, courage, teamwork, respect for rules and laws, respect for self and others, community spirit and solidarity, as well as fun and enjoyment

Emphasizing that PE, PA and sport should seek to promote stronger bonds between people, solidarity, mutual respect and understanding, and respect for the integrity and dignity of every human being

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL LEARNING

WHY Physical Education

is important for intercultural learning?

Schools in most cases are multicultural environment engaging children from different social, religious and cultural backgrounds

In multicultural school environment, a “cultural gap” can exist, due to differences in habits, beliefs and norms between staff and pupils (Wyant et al., 2020, p. 526)

Physical Education is an educational process aimed at developing skills, shaping attitudes and behaviors, and providing experiences that can be used by children even after they finish school, throughout their adult life. Different targeted activities conducted during PE classes foster students’ cooperation, responsibility, solidarity, respect for opponents, fair play, and support for peers (Dyson, 2001; Dyson & Rubin, 2003; Hellison, 2003).

School-based PE encourages social inclusion by inherently connecting motor, emotional, cognitive and social skills (Smith et al., 2021). PE cultivates values like tolerance, respect, and appreciation for cultural diversity, preparing students for a globalized world.

Schools and school-based PE has a vital role in multicultural school environment as schools can prepare future citizens for peaceful co-existence in an increasingly diverse and changing society (Grimminger-Seidensticker & Möhwald, 2017).

Engaging students in different types of activities, dances, traditional games and cultural sports helps break down cultural, social, and linguistic barriers, fostering a sense of community and belonging. Incorporating traditional games and sports into PE curriculum encourages students to value and celebrate diversity.

Physical Education has a great potential to promote intercultural competence due to its structure, goals and nature of the activities

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL LEARNING

WHY Physical Education is important for intercultural learning?

1

INVOLVEMENT

PE contents and activities support interaction and engagement of pupil regardless their gender, religion, cultural background

2

THE LANGUAGE OF MOVEMENT

Movement is the main language of P. The PE contents provides lot of possibility for both verbal and non-verbal communication. The lack of knowledge of the host language is not a barrier to participation at PE classes.

DIVERSITY

Different languages and cultures are not an exclusion criterion of participation at PE classes

3

PE CONTENTS

PE contents, such dance and games, especially traditional dances and traditional games, are great opportunity for students to present and share their cultural background and learn for other cultures (Giosos, 2000; Clements & Kinzle, 2002; Koutsoura, 2010)

4

VALUES

Participation in different games and activities supports fair play and understanding, supports development of positive self – image, self – respect and self – esteem. Students learn to value themselves, other students, respect others and treat everyone equally. These helps students understanding that all people have equal rights and obligations as citizens of a democratic society (Trudeau & Shephard, 2005).

5

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL LEARNING

HOW to DO IT?

- ❑ Apply **Universal Design for Learning (UDL)** (Con-Powers et al., 2006, Meyer, Rose, & Gordon, 2014)
- ❑ UDL envisages the principles that learning environments and activities can **involve all children without difference;**
- ❑ The UDL framework promotes **three core principles** for teachers to build into their teaching practice.

Multiple means of representation

- is the **WHAT** of learning and relates to the content in a variety of ways.
- Selection of contents
- Being clear about how material connects to children's lives will support understanding by connecting new information to what they already know.

Multiple means of engagement

- is the **WHY** of learning and relates to how to enhance student's motivation to learn.
- Find ways to motivate students to learn; connect with their interests
- In engaging children by using different strategies: giving them choice and autonomy, offering tasks that are authentic and meaningful

Multiple means of action and expression

- Is the **HOW** of learning
- Selection of strategies
- It provides a variety of ways for children to express what they know so that each child is assessed in ways that are best suited to their abilities (group work, pairs, peer – teaching etc)

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HOW to incorporate intercultural learning contents into PE classes?

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PE CONTENTS SUPPORTIVE FOR BUILDING INTERCULTURAL AND SOCIAL COMPETENCES

- Traditional games
- Cooperative games
- Dances (traditional dances)
- Traditional sports

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SUGGESTIONS HOW TO IMPLEMENT INTERCULTURAL LEARNING AND SOCIAL ACTIVITIES IN PE CLASS

Intercultural learning can be implemented in many ways within PE classes at both primary and secondary school levels. The goal is not to change the existing curriculum but to add value to it by adding elements of intercultural learning.

Disciplines – (Example DANCES)

Use intercultural content when introducing a new discipline, its origin, popularity among countries, how is done in different countries

Warm-up phase & Cool down phase

different games with intercultural content

(see examples of activities under Step 3: design and plan)

Special intercultural classes within PE schedule

Activities and games that support intercultural learning and societal dimensions

(see examples of activities under Step 3: design and plan)

Projects for students

Use a project-based learning approach and engage students in projects on topics related to intercultural elements of dances and sports.

Define some aspects of intercultural learning, appoint students in groups, and allow them to search, design, present, reflect, evaluate.

Cross-curricular activities

Combined classes with music, art, geography, ethics

Activities related to special days/extracurricular activities

School trips; Religious or national holidays; Europe day;

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION IN PE TEACHING

Example from practice – implementation of didactic scenario with primary school children by the teacher ZD

Intercultural Puzzle
Preparation of puzzle pieces

Laminated, cut and shared out at least one piece from each puzzle into baskets. I also put in a marker and recording page to write "what it is" and "where it's from". I placed one piece from each puzzle as the to start each puzzle for the group.

Example from practice – teacher ZD

Students are organised into lines. The baskets are in the middle of the field in front of each line and the students pick up a piece of the puzzle and run to the end of the field to their puzzle making spot. The person who placed the last puzzle piece, comes back and tells the group that was the last one, they all run back, make the puzzle properly and answer the question prompt page.

Regular PE classes

- ❑ Use intercultural games at the beginning of the school year, especially with newly formed classes, to help students get to know each other. This will also contribute to building group cohesion.
- ❑ During warm-up and cool-down phases, incorporate various movement games and activities that link to intercultural themes (refer to some of the didactic scenarios below).
- ❑ In the main part of the physical education (PE) class, utilize different games and activities. This can also serve as an opportunity for cross-subject learning by integrating elements from music, art, geography, history, and ethics.
- ❑ When introducing a new sport or discipline, discuss its origin, the country where it was invented, how it was traditionally practiced, and how it is played today. This can be expanded into a project for students to explore the background of specific sports in greater depth.

SEE THE [LIST OF EXAMPLES](#) OF ACTIVITIES AND GAMES PROVIDED UNDER [STEP 3](#) AND FIND MORE IDEAS THAT FIT INTO YOUR CONTEXT

SUGGESTIONS FOR IMPLEMENTATION IN PE TEACHING

PROJECTS FOR STUDENTS

- ❑ Intercultural learning through physical education (PE) and sports can be used to support students' independent learning by employing a project-based learning approach.
- ❑ Students can work in groups on a project that integrates sport, movement, and intercultural learning. Topics could include traditional dances from a specific country (either the country of origin of some students in the group or a country they are interested in), popular sports from various countries, and more.
- ❑ As part of the project, students should research their chosen topic, identify relevant activities, games, and dances, learn some of these, and present their findings and activities to their peers in class. The entire class participates in this process, allowing for collaborative learning. Students should also collect feedback and reflect on their learning experience.

Teachers can support students by suggesting possible topics, guiding the research process, and facilitating the presentation of content.

ACTIVITIES RELATED TO THE CELEBRATION OF SPECIAL DAYS

Intercultural learning through physical education and sports can be integrated into the celebration of special days or national holidays. This approach aims to raise awareness about the beauty of diversity and the importance of differences.

Additionally, intercultural activities and games can be organized during school trips, holidays, and other school celebrations. These events allow students to express their diverse backgrounds, such as through a day of traditional clothing or a day of international music and dance.

International days related to sport, culture and diversity	Day of celebration
Day of Europe	9th May)
International Children's Day	
International Day for the Elimination of Racial Discrimination	21st March
International Day of Sport for Development and Peace	6th April
World Health Day	7th April
International Day of Living Together in Peace	16th May
World Fair Play Day	19th May
World Day for Cultural Diversity for Dialogue and Development	21st May
World Football Day	25th May
World Bicycle Day	3rd June
UN Day	24th October

PHYSICAL EDUCATION AND INTERCULTURAL LEARNING

STRATEGIES THAT CAN HELP YOU

CONTENTS

Incorporate different types of activities following the interests of all students

Provide alternative activities that can allow all students to participate a meaningful way

Try to relate PE content with another subject.
Explore about countries, traditions, music, sports

COMMUNICATION

Establish clear expectations for behavior emphasis inclusivity, respect for differences, and tolerance

Use inclusive language
try to avoid ethnic, racial gender and other stereotypes

Encourage teamwork, collaboration, open discussion and honest communication

Address any instance of bullying or exclusion immediately

Ask feedback from students for how to improve the inclusive environment

STUDENTS AUTONOMY

Provide opportunities students to take leadership and different roles (ex: captain of the activity)

Give students tasks to search for a particular topic (ex: music and dances, sports)

Encourage students to search for different activities and present them

Encourage students to search for different activities and present them

ARE YOU READY FOR THE NEXT STEP?

Visit our webpage and find out different examples of activities created to support the development of intercultural and social competencies

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